

Australian Research Data Commons

ARDC Persistent Identifiers Policy

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Category	Position Statement
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Content enquiries	contact@ardc.edu.au
Related documents	Policy on Persistent Identifiers for ARDC Investments
Purpose	This policy states the ARDC's rationale, intent and broad course of action regarding persistent identifiers (PIDs)

Policy

ARDC collaborates with a range of partners to establish underpinning infrastructure that enables Australian researchers to gain competitive advantage through data. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are a core component of this national infrastructure and key to world class, global research infrastructure. As specified in the FAIR Data Principles, the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) is critical as they provide global methods to uniquely identify and connect entities in the research system such as researchers, funders, organisations, articles, datasets, software, and samples.

- By linking these entities and enabling research provenance and attribution, persistent identifiers lay the foundation for improved tracking of **research impact**.
- By precisely identifying the inputs and outputs of research, PIDs contribute to **research integrity**
- By linking scientific concepts across systems, they enable **research innovation and efficiency**

The ARDC therefore places high value on the use of PIDs in research and offers a suite of PID services to the Australian research sector to facilitate their uptake. The spread of this portfolio aims to cover off on important elements of the research enterprise (people, organisations, data, software, publications, instruments, etc).

As part of a strategy to optimise sustainable longevity and global acceptance, ARDC PID services are offered in partnership with international PID service providers (DataCite, ORCID, CrossRef, etc). Selection of PIDs in the ARDC services suite is based on an assessment of the attributes of good PID systems such as fitness for purpose, effective technical infrastructure, good governance, broad community adoption, cost effectiveness, and sustainability.

ARDC's PID services (including the Australian ORCID Consortium led by the Australian Access Federation) form part of the national research infrastructure and thus enable FAIR data outputs sector-wide in Australia in an equal, coherent, and comprehensive manner. As well as access to globally leading PID systems, ARDC provides expert advisory support for Australian research organisations integrating PIDs into their business processes.

ARDC project investment requires that data outputs be made FAIR and for this reason use appropriate PIDs for project inputs, outputs, and activities is a condition of ARDC investment.

Research is inherently global, and persistent identifier solutions for the research sector realise their greatest value at global scale. ARDC is active in coordination at the Australian level and internationally within the governance and collaboration structures of global systems. This engagement delivers an advantage to Australian research by placing Australian researchers and their outputs prominently in these emerging global research information systems and representing our interests in their governance, design and implementation.